

ERIC Forum 2

Data Management Plan

Work Package 17 - Deliverable 1

Project name	Second implementation project for the ERIC Forum
Project acronym	ERIC Forum 2
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Deliverable Title	Data Management Plan (DMP)
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Responsible Partner	Biobanking and BioMolecular Research Infrastructure – European Research Infrastructure Consortium (BBMRI-ERIC)
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Dissemination level	Public
Description of deliverable	<p>The ERIC Forum 2 DMP includes information on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Type of data that will be collected, processed and/or generated • Applied methodology and standards • Availability of data and whether data will be shared/made open access • Curation and preservation of data (including after the end of the project) <p>The DMP is developed and will be updated in line with the FAIR principles (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable), and with attention to ethical principles (including the highest standards of research integrity as set out in the ALLEA European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, as well as applicable international and national law, including the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union and the European Convention on Human Rights and its Supplementary Protocols. Appropriate procedures, policies and structures are in place to foster responsible research practices, to prevent questionable research practices and research misconduct, and to handle allegations of breaches of the principles and standards in the Code of Conduct).</p>

Executive summary

The DMP describes how information and data are collected/generated within the project. As a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) the project does not produce research data. The project will collect personal data of project partners and key stakeholders, and project partners' contributions to the deliverables.

However, data will be presented on the reporting platform (to be set up as part of WP1) which is already available data, starting from what is published in the ERIC Forum website, annual reports, EF brochures, newsletter and Toolkit with reference to ERICs' establishment dates, EC implementing decisions, contributions to SDGs and societal challenges, as well as KPI (key performance indicators) and SEI (socio-economic impact) data collected in the 1st ERIC Forum Project.

Document log

Issue	Date (yyyy-mm-dd)	Comment	Author/partner
1	2023-11-27	Initial version (based on DMP of ERIC Forum project, grant agreement N. 823798)	Johanna Kostenzer

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1. Data summary

Purpose of data collection and relation to project objectives

Data will be collected from project partners and stakeholders to fulfil the objectives of the projects, which are:

- Develop and put into operation an online platform that will provide updated data and information on the ERICs accessible to the Commission, ESFRI and other ERA stakeholders, and the general public, and identify more detailed data and information that could also be made accessible;
- Set-up and implement specific working groups to tackle joint challenges regarding the implementation of the ERIC Regulation and services such as employment issues, VAT exemption practices, procurement rules, communication, as well as visibility of ERICs and eligibility for national funding;
- Ensure synergies and compatibility with European political priorities, in particular with those that are at the core of ERICs' interest, and ensure overall alignment with the activities and outcomes of the ERA Policy Agenda to "strengthen sustainability, accessibility and resilience of research infrastructures in the ERA";
- Identify possible administrative back-office resources and services that could be shared among the ERICs and develop a strategy on how to establish and maintain such shared resources and services beyond the duration of the project;
- Reinforce and further develop the outreach of the ERIC Forum community to relevant audiences by supporting common communication and outreach activities;
- Develop relevant guidance documents, trainings, and best practices that would support not only the ERICs-to-be, but also the established ERICs across; and
- Ensure the operation of the secretariat of the Executive Board of ERIC Forum and maintain and further develop ERIC Forum Executive Board's external representation, in particular with the Commission, ESFRI, other EU institutions, and other ERA relevant stakeholders.

Types and formats of data generated/collected

Within the project, the following data will be collected:

- Personal information of the project participants and key stakeholders, including name/s, contact details, affiliations, function within their organisations, interest in the project's activities
- Best practices and experiences (reports, examples, interviews, etc.) from the project partners and key stakeholders related to the creation, management and implementation of ERICs

The project will generate:

- Reports, policy papers, best practices based on the information provided by the project partners and key stakeholders

Re-use of existing data

Data that will be presented on the reporting platform (to be set up as part of WP1) is already available, starting from what is published in the ERIC Forum website, annual reports, EF brochures, newsletter and Toolkit with reference to ERICs' establishment dates, EC implementing decisions, contributions to SDGs and societal challenges, as well as KPI+SEI data collected in the 1st ERIC Forum Project.

Origin of the data

The data will originate directly from the project partners and the key stakeholders identified.

2. FAIR data

Data collected/generated that are part of the project's deliverables, as per the Grant Agreement, will be made public via the project's website and information platform.

3. Responsibility for DMP

The project coordinator (BBMRI-ERIC) is responsible to set up, implement, and update the DMP. The Project Management Team (PMT) will assess the DMP periodically and propose edits if needed.

Long term preservation of the data collected is crucial for the European research infrastructures ecosystem. For this, the project is putting in place an information platform that builds on the ERIC Forum toolbox from ERIC Forum project 1. This will establish a sustainable pool of data for different groups of stakeholders.

4. Data security

Backups

All data will be stored on the project online platform (SharePoint) that provides an online backup.

Physical backups will be created by the project officers at regular intervals. Backups will be stored by the project coordinator within the internal BBMRI-ERIC Servers. The backups will be stored for the duration of the project, and then passed on the Secretariat of the ERIC Forum, as legacy information linked to the activities of the Forum.

Right to access/correct/erase personal data

The right of users to access/ correct/ erase personal data will be ensured, with exception in certain circumstances:

- During the project: users can contact the project coordinator and request access/ correction(s)/ deletion of their personal data
- After completion of the project: users can contact the ERIC Forum Secretariat at ericforum2@bbmri-eric.eu and request access/ correction(s)/ deletion of their personal data

External participants of the project and those who did not sign the Consortium Agreement will always be solicited for their consent and informed of the project's data protection policy when their data is being collected and processed. Likewise, their rights to access/ correct/ erase personal data will be ensured, with exception in certain circumstances.

5. Ethical aspects

The project foresees the conducting of interviews and surveys. Participants will be properly informed, in writing, about the issues related to personal data protection and other aspects of participation in surveys/interviews, in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (EU 2016/679) of the European Parliament and of the Council of April 27, 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data.